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Abror Nuritdinov

Teacher of the Department of theory and methodology of Taekwondo WTF, Karate WKF Uzbek State University of Physical Education and Sport, nuritdinov@gmail.com

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RATIO OF PERFORMANCE OF HIGHLY QUALIFIED TAEKWONDO FIGHTERS IN DIFFICULT AND EXTREME CONDITIONS

Abror Nuritdinov

**Teacher of the Department of theory and methodology of Taekwondo WTF,
Karate WKF**

Uzbek State University of Physical Education and Sport

E-mail address: nuritdinov@gmail.com

Abstract. The competitive activity of taekwondo fighters is characterized by the fact that technical and tactical tasks are solved many times. The difficulty in accurately selecting a combat action that will be effective in a particular episode of a battle is that the number of actions planned in combat, as well as their qualitative composition and the nature of the opponent's actions, are constantly changing again and again. In addition, taekwondo fighters have the opportunity to choose objectively when the appropriate solutions are single and multiple. This article covers an analysis of the competitions highly qualified taekwondo fighters have been participating in so far and its results that helps to determine the effectiveness of combat actions with different tactical characteristics, reflecting the level of preparation of taekwondo fighters to perform combat actions and reaction characteristics.

Keywords: counterattack, self-defense, self-confidence, self-doubt, self-belief, sensory barrier, taekwondo fighter, training process, competition, complex reaction.

INTRUCTION.

The results of training and competitions highly qualified taekwondo fighters have been participating in reveals that confidence in success is significantly decreases, the form of active combat is replaced by the form of active time ambush. As a consequence, it leads to a noticeable decrease in the effectiveness of fighting (*Table 1*). A lack of confidence highly qualified taekwondo fighters sometimes have is due to the objective difficulties of the activities performed, the individual

characteristics of them, as well as changes in the form of organization of the fight. A decrease in activity is the result of an increase in the lack of information and its subjective reflection in the form of trust.

Table - 1

Indicators of fighting in different situations

Fights of varying intensity	Effectiveness		Compatibility of tactical solutions		Managing self-confidence prior to competition		A form of fighting		
	<i>Success</i>	<i>Defeat</i>	<i>Compatible</i>	<i>Not compatible</i>	<i>Self-belief</i>	<i>Self-doubt</i>	<i>Active</i>	<i>In the form of active time ambush</i>	<i>In the form of an ambush</i>
Fights in trainings	82	18	63	37	81	19	69	19	12
Fights in competitions	56	44	52	48	47	53	36	52	12

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

The aim of the research is to provide information on ratio of performance of highly qualified taekwondo fighters in difficult and extreme conditions, as well as this article analysed the following methods:

- scientific and methodological literature;
- observation;
- interviews;
- surveys;

- mathematical- statistical analysis

The tactical means of actions depend on many components such as to move, initiative in fighting, and the ability of athletes to react. It can be clear from the table that most of the movements, which have tactical characteristics that reflect the level of preparation in training, are performed by highly qualified taekwondo fighters in advance. Analyzing the data related to the reactions of athletes, it is noted that most of the movements are performed conditionally. Actions performed by selection and transition from one action to another are based on complex reactions and are rarely used. These very known difficulties that arise due to sensory barriers in these fights are explained by the need to predict the long-term effects of taekwondo fighters' interactions.

Competition pictures (attack and counter-attack)

However, the effectiveness of the types of combat actions shown is high and stable enough. Experts link the effectiveness of the execution of confrontational punches to the sense of time, which probably leads to certain difficulties in their use of highly qualified taekwondo fighters.

Competition pictures (counter-attacks)

This requires a high level of development of special reactions from them, rapid and accurate comprehension of the necessary information, its rapid processing, tactical risk. Such qualities are more characteristic of highly qualified taekwondo fighters. An analysis of the actions of highly qualified taekwondo fighters elucidate that attacks are more widely used than other means of combat and are very effective. Among the means of resisting attacks in competitions, trying to move with a counter-attack ahead of the opponent is effective and efficient. This is explained by the fact that counter-offensive movements are technically easier to perform than defenses with arms or torso.

Competition pictures (counter-attacks)

However, the effectiveness of counter-attacks in competitive battles is much lower than in freestyle combat in training. About 80% of the total number of fights in the competition are done with delay. Counter-attacks are usually actions that are simple, conditioned, and performed by moving from one action to another. The scope of application of counter-protections is not large, which is due to the fact that they are very difficult to implement. It is clear that in taekwondo WTF, the execution time of a normal movement is less than the time of a fighter`s normal movement reaction. The technical simplicity of moving from one action to another in response to an impact on an opening body part suggests that high-performance countermeasures are frequently premeditated, conditioned, and selective. According to the research data, it can be concluded that a comparison of a set of combat movements with different intensities, used in training and competitions, helps to identify certain patterns, and taking them into account will serve to enhance the process of training and competitions.

To optimize the process of technical and tactical improvement of highly qualified taekwondo fighters, it is of paramount importance to lift the specialization of training exercises. To achieve this, their performance in training should be as close as possible to the conditions of the competition.

Taekwondo training pictures

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The highly qualified taekwondo fighters are capable of fighting in different levels of intensity, and it is due to a reflection of their individual characteristics. An analysis of the main types of movement shows that the volume of attacks in training is more than 40%, with the exception of R.N. (19.6%) in all tested highly qualified taekwondo fighters. The figure was above 50% in only two fighters, R.M. (54.3%) and B.J. (52.5%) respectively. The effectiveness of attacks in trainings is not high enough - almost half of the tested taekwondo fighters scored less than 50%. At the same time, it should be acknowledged that the effectiveness of the use of attacks in trainings is noticeably high, U.T. (60.3%), A.B. (68.4%) and U.A. (70.2%) can be striking examples. The extent of application of the protections varies from 7.3% (H.V.) to 41.1% (R.N.), but this index is higher than 25% in the majority of athletes, and this figure exceeded in only three taekwondo fighters: 30% (Sh.F.), 32.5% (R.N.) and 41.1 (A.D.). Then, in only two athletes that figure was more than 50%, namely 52.7% (R.N.) and 56 % (D.J.).

The volume of counter-attacks of the most highly qualified taekwondo fighters is not large in the set of combat actions in training. In only three athletes (A.B., X.V., and X.V.) that figure accounted for 25% (30.9%, 28.8% and 85.1 respectively), and in nine athletes the volume of counter-attacks was less than 20

percent (Sh.D. (17.1%), U.T. (19.4%), R.N. (16.5%), A.D. (16.5%), S.D. (19.7%), B.J. (17.1%), B.Sh. (17.1%), Sh.Sh. (15.6%) and D.J. (18.2%) correspondingly. However, the effectiveness of counter-attacks in the controlled group is high enough - more than 55%, except Sh.M. (52.6%) and A.D. (52.6%).

The analysis of stroke was absolutely large - individual differences in the range from 2.7% (N.S.) to 20.2% (R.N.). Moreover, only three taekwondo fighters U.T., X.V., R.N. experienced 11.2%, 13.8% and 20.2% respectively, but in half of the fighters, the figure did not exceed 5%. In highly qualified taekwondo fighters, the effectiveness of attacks in training was seen more than 50%. Only three athletes (Sh.D, J.B, A.D) used counterblow with the following results: 45.9%, 49.8%, and 49.0%, relatively. At the same time, a high efficiency R.N (79.4%) of the use of counterattacks was noted. In most of the tested taekwondo fighters, the use of defenses against the counter attack in training fights was noted in very small quantities, which does not allow an objective assessment of their effectiveness. In only three athletes the volume of defenses against the counter attack was more than 3% (U.T (6.3%), B.Sh (3.6%) and Sh.Sh (5.3%)). In addition, only one athlete, U.T (58.7%), experienced optimal results of self-defense (58.7%). From a personal perspective, the level of training of the tested taekwondo fighters does not allow the use of technically complex movements in taekwondo fights.

In tournaments, the effectiveness of attacks has been improving. The spread of the indicators also ranged from Sh.M (47.3%) to H.V (63.4%) while a marginal difference in training fights was from S.D (40.5%) to X.V (70.2%) In competitions, the volumes of highly qualified taekwondo fighters self-defenses are slightly decreased. In only one athlete, R.N, that index was 30% (correspondingly 30.3%), which is low compared to training fights. (B.Sh - from 28.4% to 11.5%; Sh.Sh - from 28.3% to 14.5%; D.J - from 27.2% to 11.3% each). The effectiveness of the response after defending against attacks in competitions has improved. Approximately, half of the athletes perform movements with more than 50% enhancement Sh.D (52.5%), U.T (50.2%), R.N (55.0%), A.D (52.2%), S.D (54.2%) and R.J (54.2%) as well.

CONCLUSION.

Taekwondo fighters

have significantly improved the use of counterattacks in competitions, were higher than 25% in most athletes, and five athletes: N.S (30, 9%), A.B (31.6%), K.V (30.4%), Sh.Sh (32.6%) and D.J (35%) witnessed an increased of more than 30%. However, the effectiveness of counterattacks in competitions was slightly worse than in training sessions. In trainings ten athletes reached the level of 60%, yet in competitions only six athletes achieved that figure, they were G.I (63.3%), B.J (60.0%), Han (67.8), R.N (60.9%), B.Sh (61.9%) and Sh.Sh (60.0%). F.A, in competitions, should pay great attention mostly to high volumes of strokes (6.9%), this is because, he can escape opponents' attacks by doing more counterattacks, since the volume of counterattacks of him is high enough (33.1%). Such an athlete has a high efficiency of counterattacks and counterblows, 67.8%, and 66.2%, respectively, which allows him to win.

An analysis of the performance of counterdefenses as well as counterattacks in competitions helps us to determine that the majority of the athletes examined hardly ever use these types of combat actions. In only two taekwondo fighters, U.T, A.B, the volume of counterdefenses and counterattacks was slightly more than 3% (3.1% and 3.2%, respectively), while their effectiveness was 39.8% and 34.9%. Therefore, they should use the most difficult tactics and techniques to achieve the highest score. It is suggested that coaches train athletes in better decision-making by teaching them to work on their own and intended attacks to score maximum. In taekwondo, not only the level of technique, physical and psychological preparation, but also the main character traits are manifested. Tactical skill is manifested in the ability to neutralize the strengths of the enemy, use the weaknesses of opponents and the ability to apply the individual style of combat.

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